

Probabilistic Logic of k -Valued Formulaic Events Without Combinatorial Explosion

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ABSTRACT

In a finite-valued k -valued propositional calculus, the truth table of a formula containing n variables consists of k^n rows, which leads to an exponential growth in the number of possible interpretations and gives rise to the problem of combinatorial explosion [1]. In the works of Pearl [5] and Russell and Norvig [6], devoted to probabilistic inference and artificial intelligence, it is shown that as the number of variables and dependencies increases, the computational complexity of logical and probabilistic inference grows rapidly. For many-valued logical systems, this results in an exponential increase in the number of interpretations and hinders the application of traditional truth-table methods in intelligent systems.

This paper proposes a probabilistic logic of events intended for knowledge representation and probabilistic inference in artificial intelligence systems. The proposed approach is based on event algebra and probability theory and makes it possible to significantly reduce the computational complexity associated with combinatorial explosion.

Keywords: probabilistic logic, artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, probabilistic inference, event algebra, many-valued logic, combinatorial explosion.

1. Introduction

Probabilistic logic [1, 5, 6] is one of the most important tools for representing and processing uncertain knowledge in expert and intelligent systems. Probabilistic logic makes it possible to take into account the degree of confidence in the truth of statements. Such methods are widely used in expert diagnostic systems, decision-support systems, intelligent agents, and artificial-intelligence systems. However, as the number of variables and states grows, the problem of combinatorial explosion arises, which motivates the search for new logical and probabilistic models of inference. In this paper the combinatorial explosion is eliminated for k -valued formulaic events.

2. Two-Valued Probabilistic Logic of Formulaic Events

We transform the two-valued propositional calculus [1] into a probabilistic two-valued logic of formal events.

Consider an experiment S in which random events A and B may or may not occur. We introduce a function $\varphi(x)$ whose domain is the set of random events arising in the realization of the experiment. If event A occurs, then $\varphi(A) = 1$; if it does not occur, then $\varphi(A) = 0$. The range of $\varphi(x)$ is $\{0,1\}$. The function $\varphi(x)$ is called the *occurrence function*.

Using the operations \wedge , \vee , and \neg , new events can be obtained.

Definition 1. The random event $\neg A$ occurs if and only if event A does not occur.

Table 1. Occurrence of the random event $\neg A$.

$\varphi(A)$	$\varphi(\neg A)$
1	0
0	1

The random event $\neg A$ is called the *negation* of event A .

Definition 2. The random event $A \vee B$ occurs if at least one of the events A or B occurs.

Table 2. Occurrence of the random event $A \vee B$.

$\varphi(A)$	$\varphi(B)$	$\varphi(A \vee B)$
1	1	1
0	1	1
1	0	1
0	0	0

The random event $A \vee B$ is called the *disjunction*, with disjuncts A and B .

Definition 3. The event $A \wedge B$ occurs if and only if both events A and B occur.

Table 3. Occurrence of the random event $A \wedge B$.

$\varphi(A)$	$\varphi(B)$	$\varphi(A \wedge B)$
1	1	1
0	1	0
1	0	0
0	0	0

The random event $A \wedge B$ is called the *conjunction* of events A and B , with conjuncts A and B . Instead of $A \wedge B$ one sometimes writes AB .

Remark. Material implication $A \rightarrow B$ is not considered here; it is not suitable. For example, suppose event A did not occur and event B did not occur, yet the event $A \rightarrow B$ “occurred”?

Consider an experiment S having various outcomes, and suppose that the complete list of possible outcomes is known in advance, together with their probabilities. We consider the case in which the set of distinct outcomes is finite. The distinct outcomes are also called *elementary*

events and are denoted ω_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The set of elementary events is denoted by the capital Greek letter

$$\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}.$$

It is assumed that to each elementary event $\omega_i \in \Omega$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) a non-negative number $P(\omega_i)$ is assigned, called the *probability of occurrence* of the elementary event [3], and

$$P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_n) = 1.$$

Remark 1. In the realization of experiment S , exactly one of the elementary events ω_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) can occur. That is, if $\varphi(\omega_i) = 1$ for some i , then $\varphi(\omega_j) = 0$ for every $j \neq i$.

Definition 4. A disjunction of elementary events is called a *disjunctive sum of elementary events* (DSEE).

Example. $\omega_1 \vee \omega_3 \vee \omega_6$ is a three-term disjunctive sum of elementary events.

Note. Each $\omega_i \in \Omega$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) will be regarded as a one-term disjunctive sum of elementary events.

Definition 5.

1. Every DSEE is a formulaic event.
2. If A is a formulaic event, then $\neg A$ is a formulaic event.
3. If A and B are formulaic events, then $(A \vee B)$ and $(A \wedge B)$ are formulaic events.
4. A formulaic event can be obtained only by applying rules 1, 2, and 3.

The set of all two-valued formulaic events is denoted SF2E.

Definition 6. Let $B(\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m})$ be a formula of events composed of the elementary events $\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m}$. An elementary event ω_{k_i} is called *non-fictitious* for the formula of events $B(\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m})$ if there exist values

$$\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = \alpha_1, \dots, \varphi(\omega_{k_{i-1}}) = \alpha_{i-1}, \varphi(\omega_{k_{i+1}}) = \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = \alpha_m$$

such that

$$B(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{i-1}, 0, \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \alpha_m) \neq B(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{i-1}, 1, \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \alpha_m);$$

otherwise the elementary event ω_{k_i} is called *fictitious*.

Definition 7. For a formulaic event B , the number of non-fictitious elementary events occurring in it is called its *rank*. The list of non-fictitious elementary events of the formula of events B is denoted NFEFF(B) (non-fictitious elementary events of the formula).

Algorithm for computing the probability of a formula of events. Let B be a formula of events of rank m , composed of the non-fictitious elementary events $\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m}$. Then, for this formula of events B , the occurrence table for the argument (taking Remark 1 into account) consists of m rows:

- in row 1, column 1, $\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = 1$, and in this row $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$ for $j \neq 1$ ($j = 2, \dots, m$);
- in row 2, column 2, $\varphi(\omega_{k_2}) = 1$, and in this row $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$ for $j \neq 2$;
-
in row m , column m , $\varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = 1$, and in this row $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$ for $j \neq m$.

The probability of the formula of events B is computed by the formula

$$P(B) = \sum_{\{i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } i\}} P(\omega_{k_i}).$$

If every value in the column $\varphi(B)$ of the table equals 0, then $P(B) = 0$.

Definition 8. $SUEE(B) = \bigcup_{\{i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } i\}} \{\omega_{k_i}\}$.

$SUEE(B)$ denotes a *set of upcoming elementary events* of B .

Definition 9. If $SUEE(Q) \subseteq SUEE(B)$, then we say that the formulaic event B *probably logically* follows from the formulaic event Q ,

Definition 10. If $SUEE(Q_1 \wedge \dots \wedge Q_m) \subseteq SUEE(B)$, then we say that the formulaic event B *probably logically* follows from the formulaic event Q_1, \dots, Q_m .

Example 1. Let $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_6\}$ and let the probabilities $P(\omega_i), i = 1, \dots, 6$, be given. Consider the formula of events $C = (\omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_1) \wedge (\omega_1 \vee \omega_2 \vee \omega_3)$.

Since, in the experiment under consideration, only one of the elementary events $\omega_i \in \Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_6\}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$) occurs, the occurrence table for this formula consists of 6 rows.

Table 4. Event $C = (\omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_1) \wedge (\omega_1 \vee \omega_2 \vee \omega_3)$, with $A = (\omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_1)$ and $B = (\omega_1 \vee \omega_2 \vee \omega_3)$.

No.	$\varphi(\omega_1)$	$\varphi(\omega_2)$	$\varphi(\omega_3)$	$\varphi(\omega_4)$	$\varphi(\omega_5)$	$\varphi(\omega_6)$	$\varphi(A)$	$\varphi(B)$	$\varphi(C)$
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
3	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1
4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
6	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

The probability is $P(C) = P(\omega_1) + P(\omega_3)$, since in the first row $\varphi(\omega_1) = 1$ and $\varphi(C) = 1$, in the third row $\varphi(\omega_3) = 1$ and $\varphi(C) = 1$, while in the remaining rows $\varphi(C) = 0$.

Definition 11. $L_2' = (\Omega, SF2E, P)$ is called a *two-valued probabilistic logical space*.

Definition 12. If $SUEE(Q) = \Omega$, then Q is called a *certain* formulaic event.

Definition 13. If $SUEE(Q) = \emptyset$, then Q is called an *impossible* formulaic event.

Definition 14. Two probabilistic formulas Q and C are called *equivalent*, written $Q \equiv C$, if $SUEE(Q) = SUEE(C)$. Clearly, if $Q \equiv C$, then $P(C) = P(Q)$.

Definition 15. We say that formulaic events A and B are *mutually exclusive* (incompatible) if $P(A \wedge B) = 0$, i.e. $SUEE(A \wedge B) = \emptyset$.

Remark. We will always work with classical sets, that is, sets without repeated elements.

From the algorithm for computing the probability of a formula of events, the following hold:

- For any formulaic event A , $0 \leq P(A) \leq 1$.
- Since, when the event table for $Y = \omega_1 \vee \dots \vee \omega_n$ is constructed, the column $\varphi(Y)$ equals 1 in all rows, $P(\omega_1 \vee \dots \vee \omega_n) = P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_n) = 1$.
- $SUEE(\neg A) = \Omega \setminus SUEE(A)$, hence $P(\neg A) = 1 - P(A)$.
- For any formulaic events A and B , since:
 $SUEE(A \cup B) = (SUEE(A) \cup SUEE(B)) \setminus SUEE(A \cap B)$, then
 $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$.
- Definition 15 it follows. For any formulaic events A and B , if they are incompatible, then
 $P(A \cup B) = P(A) + P(B) - P(A \cap B)$. (additivity)

Thus Kolmogorov's axioms [3] hold.

Theorem. If a formula of events B in the probability space over $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$ is not an impossible event, then it is equivalent to a DSEE.

Proof. Construct the event table for B and, on its basis, construct $SUEE(B)$. Put

$$Q = \bigvee \{ \omega_i \mid \omega_i \in SUEE(B) \}.$$

From the algorithm for constructing this disjunctive sum and from the properties of the operation \bigvee , we obtain at once that $Q \equiv B$. ■

Example 2. Let $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_6\}$, and suppose $\varphi(Q)$ equals 1 only in rows 1,3,5, and 6.

Table 5. Occurrence table of Q .

No.	$\varphi(\omega_1)$	$\varphi(\omega_2)$	$\varphi(\omega_3)$	$\varphi(\omega_4)$	$\varphi(\omega_5)$	$\varphi(\omega_6)$	$\varphi(Q)$
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
6	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

Then $DSEE(Q) = \omega_1 \vee \omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_6$. Construct the event table for $B = \omega_1 \vee \omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_6$.

Table 6. Occurrence table of $B = \omega_1 \vee \omega_3 \vee \omega_5 \vee \omega_6$.

No.	$\varphi(\omega_1)$	$\varphi(\omega_2)$	$\varphi(\omega_3)$	$\varphi(\omega_4)$	$\varphi(\omega_5)$	$\varphi(\omega_6)$	$\varphi(B)$
1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
4	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
6	0	0	0	0	0	1	1

Therefore $Q \equiv B$.

Given the two-valued probabilistic logical space $L_2' = (\Omega, \text{SF2E}, P)$, to each $Q \in \text{SF2E}$ we associate the set

$$F = \{ \text{SUEE}(Q) \mid Q \in \text{SF2E} \}.$$

Then F is a family of subsets of Ω , and (Ω, F, P) is a probability space [1].

In classical probabilistic logic, the probability table of an n -variable formula consists of 2^n rows and is therefore explosive, whereas in the present work a formulaic event requires at most n rows.

3. Three-Valued Probabilistic Logic of Formulaic Events Based on Łukasiewicz's Three-Valued Logic

3.1. Three-Valued Probabilistic Logic of Events (Łukasiewicz)

In Jan Łukasiewicz's three-valued logic, each statement takes one of three values: 1 — true; $1/2$ — undetermined / possible; 0 — false.

Table 7. Łukasiewicz logical operations [4].

A	B	$\neg A$	$A \wedge B$	$A \vee B$
1	1	0	1	1
1	$1/2$	0	$1/2$	1
1	0	0	0	1
$1/2$	1	$1/2$	$1/2$	1
$1/2$	$1/2$	$1/2$	$1/2$	$1/2$
$1/2$	0	$1/2$	0	$1/2$
0	1	1	0	1
0	$1/2$	1	0	$1/2$
0	0	1	0	0

For convenience we replace $1/2$ by 2. Then Table 7 becomes Table 8.

Table 8. Łukasiewicz logical operations (with 1/2 replaced by 2).

$\varphi(A)$	$\varphi(B)$	$\varphi(\neg A)$	$\varphi(A \wedge B)$	$\varphi(A \vee B)$
1	1	0	1	1
1	2	0	2	1
1	0	0	0	1
2	1	2	2	1
2	2	2	2	2
2	0	2	0	2
0	1	1	0	1
0	2	1	0	2
0	0	1	0	0

To construct the probability algebra of the three-valued logic of events based on Łukasiewicz's three-valued logic, we introduce a function $\varphi(x)$ whose domain is the set of random events arising in the realization of some experiment. If A is a random event, then: if event A affects the expert (or intelligent) system positively, $\varphi(A) = 1$; if neutrally, $\varphi(A) = 2$; if event A does not occur, $\varphi(A) = 0$. The range of $\varphi(x)$ is $\{0,1,2\}$.

3.2. Three-Valued Probabilistic Logic of Formulaic Events (Łukasiewicz)

Consider an experiment S having various outcomes, and suppose that the complete list of possible outcomes and their probabilities is known in advance. We consider the case in which the set of distinct outcomes is finite. The distinct outcomes are called elementary events and are denoted ω_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$). The set of elementary events, denoted by the capital Greek letter $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n\}$, is called the probability space. It is assumed that each outcome ω_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) can take three values:

- if $\varphi(\omega_i) = 0$, the elementary event ω_i did not occur;
- if $\varphi(\omega_i) = 1$, the elementary event ω_i occurred with probability $P(\omega_{i1}) \geq 0$;
- if $\varphi(\omega_i) = 2$, the elementary event ω_i occurred with probability $P(\omega_{i2}) \geq 0$.

$$P(\omega_{i1}) + P(\omega_{i2}) = P(\omega_i), \quad P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_n) = 1.$$

Remark 2. In the realization of experiment S , exactly one of the elementary events ω_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) can occur. That is, if $\varphi(\omega_i) = 1$ or 2 for some i , then $\varphi(\omega_j) = 0$ for every $j \neq i$.

Definitions 4 and 5 also remain valid here. When computing the logical value of a formulaic event, Table 8 is used. The set of all formulaic events of the three-valued Łukasiewicz logic is denoted SF3E.

Definition 16. Let $B(\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m})$ be a formula of events composed of the elementary events $\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m}$. An elementary event ω_{k_i} is called *non-fictitious* for the formula of events $B(\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m})$ if there exist values

$$\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = \alpha_1, \dots, \varphi(\omega_{k_{i-1}}) = \alpha_{i-1}, \varphi(\omega_{k_{i+1}}) = \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = \alpha_m$$

and values $s, t \in \{0,1,2\}$ with $s \neq t$ such that

$$B(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{i-1}, s, \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \alpha_m) \neq B(\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_{i-1}, t, \alpha_{i+1}, \dots, \alpha_m);$$

otherwise the elementary event ω_{k_i} is called *fictitious*.

Definition 17. For a formulaic event B , the number of non-fictitious elementary events occurring in it is called its *rank*. The list of non-fictitious elementary events of the formula of events B is denoted $\text{NFEEF}(B)$.

Algorithm for computing the probability of a formula of events (Łukasiewicz). Let B be a formula of events of rank m , composed of the non-fictitious elementary events $\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m}$. Then, for this formula of events B , the occurrence table for the argument (taking Remark 2 into account) consists of $3m + 3$ rows, constructed by assigning to each elementary event in turn the values 1 and 2:

1 row 1 column =1, $\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = 1$ in this row $j \neq 1$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$ $j=2\dots m$

2 row 2 column , $\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = 2$, in this row $j \neq 2$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

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2m+1 row 2m+1 column $\varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = 1$, in this row $j \neq m$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

2m+2 row 2m+2 column $\varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = 2$, in this row $j \neq m$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

The probability of the formula of events B is then computed by means of the following definitions.

Definition 18. $P(B^{(1)}) = \sum_{\{i=\overline{0,m}; i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } 2i+1\}} P(\omega_{k_{2i+1}})$.

Definition 19. $\text{SUEE}(B^{(1)}) = \bigcup_{(i=\overline{0,m}; i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } 2i+1)} \{\omega_{k_{2i+1}}\}$.

Definition 20. $P(B^{(2)}) = \sum_{\{i=\overline{1,m+1}; i : \varphi(B)=2 \text{ in row } 2i\}} P(\omega_{k_{2i}})$.

Definition 21. $\text{SUEE}(B^{(2)}) = \bigcup_{\{i=\overline{1,m+1}; i : \varphi(B)=2 \text{ in row } 2i\}} \{\omega_{k_{2i}}\}$.

The probability of the formula of events B is

$$P(B) = P(B^{(1)}) + P(B^{(2)}).$$

If every value in the column $\varphi(B)$ of the table equals 0, then $P(B^{(1)}) = P(B^{(2)}) = P(B) = 0$.

Kolmogorov's axioms [3] here take the form:

1. For any formulaic event B , $0 \leq P(B) \leq 1$. The validity of this inequality follows from the algorithm for computing $P(B)$.
2. For any formulaic events A and B , since for each $r \in \{1,2\}$

$$\text{SUEE}(A^{(r)} \cup B^{(r)}) = \left(\text{SUEE}(A^{(r)}) \cup \text{SUEE}(B^{(r)}) \right) \setminus \text{SUEE}(A^{(r)} \cap B^{(r)}),$$

it follows that

$$P(A^{(r)} \vee B^{(r)}) = P(A^{(r)}) + P(B^{(r)}) - P(A^{(r)} \wedge B^{(r)}), \quad r = 1,2,3.$$

Hence, for each $r \in \{1,2\}$, if $\text{SUEE}(A^{(r)} \cap B^{(r)}) = \emptyset$, then $P(A^{(r)} \vee B^{(r)}) = P(A^{(r)}) + P(B^{(r)})$.

Definition 22. If $\text{SUEE}(Q^{(r)}) \subseteq \text{SUEE}(B^{(r)})$, then we say that the formulaic event $B^{(r)}$ *probably logically* follows from the formulaic event $Q^{(r)}$ $r \in \{1,2\}$,

Definition 23. If $\text{SUEE}(Q_1^r \wedge \dots \wedge Q_m^r) \subseteq \text{SUEE}(B)$, then we say that the formulaic event B *probably logically* follows from the formulaic event Q_1^r, \dots, Q_m^r . $r \in \{1,2\}$,

Remark. If we set $\text{SUEE}(B) = \text{SUEE}(B^{(1)}) \cup \text{SUEE}(B^{(2)}) \cup \text{SUEE}(B^{(3)})$, then Definitions 9 and 10 remain valid for the four-valued probabilistic logic of formulaic events.

Definition 24. $L_3' = (\{0,1,2\}, \Omega, \text{SF3E}, P)$ is called a *three-valued probabilistic logical space of Jan Łukasiewicz* (the set of all formulaic events of the three-valued Łukasiewicz logic).

Remark. If we set $\text{SUEE}(B) = \text{SUEE}(B^{(1)}) \cup \text{SUEE}(B^{(2)})$, then Definitions 9 and 10 remain valid for the three-valued probabilistic logic of formulaic events of Jan Łukasiewicz.

Remark. A table of formulas with n variables in the three-valued Łukasiewicz logic consists of 3^n rows, whereas a table of formulaic events in the three-valued probabilistic logic of formulaic events of Jan Łukasiewicz with n variables consists of $2(n+2)$ rows.

4. Four-Valued Probabilistic Logic of Formulaic Events

Consider the Cartesian product $L_2' \times L_2'$. Given the two-valued probabilistic logical space $L_2' = (\Omega, \text{SF2E}, P)$, we form

$$L_2' \times L_2' = (\{(0,0), (1,0), (0,1), (1,1)\}, \Omega \times \Omega, \text{SF2E} \times \text{SF2E}, P).$$

For convenience we denote: $(0,0)$ by 0; $(1,0)$ by 1; $(0,1)$ by 2; and $(1,1)$ by 3. The tables of the logical operations for $L_2' \times L_2'$ are as follows.

Table 9. Negation $\neg x$.

x	$\neg x$
0	3
1	2
2	1
3	0

Table 10. Disjunction $x \vee y$.

\vee	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	1	3	3
2	2	3	2	2
3	3	3	3	3

Table 11. Conjunction $x \wedge y$.

\wedge	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	0	1	0	1
2	0	0	2	2
3	0	1	2	3

In the realization of experiment S , for a formulaic event $A \in L_2' \times L_2'$:

- $A = 0$ — it does not occur;
- $A = 1$ — it affects the expert (intelligent) system negatively;
- $A = 2$ — it affects the expert (intelligent) system weakly positively;
- $A = 3$ — it affects the expert (intelligent) system strongly positively.

By the definition of the Cartesian product, if $A, B \in L_2'$ and $(A, B) \in L_2' \times L_2'$, then

$$P((A, B)) = P(A) \cdot P(B).$$

Denote $\omega_k = (\omega_i, \omega_j)$, where $k = (i - 1) \cdot n + j$. Then the set of elementary events of $\Omega \times \Omega$ can be written as

$$\Omega \times \Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_{n^2}\}.$$

By the definition of the Cartesian product,

$$P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_{n^2}) = (P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_n)) \cdot (P(\omega_1) + \dots + P(\omega_n)) = 1.$$

Algorithm for computing the probability of a formula of events. Let B be a formula of events with $B \in L_2' \times L_2'$, of rank m , composed of the non-fictitious elementary events $\omega_{k_1}, \dots, \omega_{k_m}$. Then, for this formula of events B , the occurrence table for the argument (taking Remark 1 into account) consists of $3m + 3$ rows, constructed by assigning to each elementary event in turn the values 1, 2, and 3:

1 row 1 column =1, $\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = 1$ in this row $j \neq 1$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$ $j=2\dots m$

2 row 2 column, $\varphi(\omega_{k_1}) = 2$, in this row $j \neq 2$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

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2m+1 row 2m+1 column $\varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = 1$, in this row $j \neq m$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

2m+2 row 2m+2 column $\varphi(\omega_{k_m}) = 2$, in this row $j \neq m$, $\varphi(\omega_{k_j}) = 0$

Definition 25. $P(B^{(1)}) = \sum_{i=\overline{0,m}, \{i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } 3i+1\}} P(\omega_{k_{3i+1}})$.

Definition 26. $SUEE(B^{(1)}) = \bigcup_{\{i=\overline{0,m}, i : \varphi(B)=1 \text{ in row } 3i+1\}} \{\omega_{k_{3i+1}}\}$.

Definition 27. $P(B^{(2)}) = \sum_{\{i=\overline{0,m}, i : \varphi(B)=2 \text{ in row } 3i+2\}} P(\omega_{k_{3i+2}})$.

Definition 28. $SUEE(B^{(2)}) = \bigcup_{\{i=\overline{0,m}, i : \varphi(B)=2 \text{ in row } 3i+2\}} \{\omega_{k_{3i+2}}\}$.

Definition 29. $P(B^{(3)}) = \sum_{\{i=\overline{0,m}, i : \varphi(B)=3 \text{ in row } 3i+3\}} P(\omega_{k_{3i+3}})$.

Definition 30. $SUEE(B^{(3)}) = \bigcup_{\{i=\overline{0,m}, i : \varphi(B)=3 \text{ in row } 3i+3\}} \{\omega_{k_{3i+3}}\}$.

The probability of the formula of events B is

$$P(B) = P(B^{(1)}) + P(B^{(2)}) + P(B^{(3)}).$$

If every value in the column $\varphi(B)$ of the table equals 0, then the formulaic event B did not occur, and

$$P(B^{(1)}) = P(B^{(2)}) = P(B^{(3)}) = P(B) = 0.$$

Put $Y = \omega_1 \vee \dots \vee \omega_{n^2}$. Kolmogorov's axioms here take the form:

1. For any formulaic event B , $0 \leq P(B) \leq 1$. The validity of this inequality follows from the algorithm for computing $P(B)$.
2. For any formulaic events A and B , since for each $r \in \{1,2,3\}$

$$SUEE(A^{(r)} \cup B^{(r)}) = (SUEE(A^{(r)}) \cup SUEE(B^{(r)})) \setminus SUEE(A^{(r)} \cap B^{(r)}),$$

it follows that

$$P(A^{(r)} \vee B^{(r)}) = P(A^{(r)}) + P(B^{(r)}) - P(A^{(r)} \wedge B^{(r)}), \quad r = 1,2,3.$$

Hence, for each $r \in \{1,2,3\}$, if $SUEE(A^{(r)} \cap B^{(r)}) = \emptyset$, then $P(A^{(r)} \vee B^{(r)}) = P(A^{(r)}) + P(B^{(r)})$.

Definition31. If $SUEE(Q^{(r)}) \subseteq SUEE(B^{(r)})$, then we say that the formulaic event $B^{(r)}$ probably logically follows from the formulaic event $Q^{(r)}$ $r \in \{1,2,3\}$,

Definition 32 .If $SUEE(Q_1^r \wedge \dots \wedge Q_m^r) \subseteq SUEE(B)$, then we say that the formulaic event B probably logically follows from the formulaic event Q_1^r, \dots, Q_m^r . $r \in \{1,2,3\}$,

Remark. If we set $SUEE(B) = SUEE(B^{(1)}) \cup SUEE(B^{(2)}) \cup SUEE(B^{(3)})$, then Definitions 9 and 10 remain valid for the four-valued probabilistic logic of formulaic events.

Remark. A table of formulas with n variables in four-valued logic consists of 4^n rows, whereas a table of formulaic events in the four-valued logic of formulaic events with n variables consists of $3(n + 3)$ rows.

5. Conclusion

In this work, the 2-, 3-, and 4-valued logics of formulaic events have been constructed without combinatorial explosion. Analogously, one can construct a k -valued logic of formulaic events for $k > 4$: with n variables, its table consists of $(k - 1)(n + k - 1)$ rows (without combinatorial explosion), instead of k^n rows. They can be used to create expert and intelligent systems without a combinatorial explosion.

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